

Against ethnoecocide: from far-right political violence to the collective resistance of Indigenous peoples in Brazil

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Abstract

The starting point of this paper is mapping extreme right-wing discourses about Indigenous peoples and their territories and examining how they are reclaimed and subverted through Indigenous resistance movements in Brazil. We highlight how the discursive production resulting from the largest Brazilian Indigenous conference – the Free Land Camp (*Acampamento Terra Livre - ATL*), in the editions from 2019 to 2022, responded to the attacks in speeches by the federal executive administration. For this, we revisit a few relevant concepts of the decolonial turn, outline contexts of attack and resistance to the rights of Indigenous peoples in the period, summarise results of our previous analysis on discourses by the executive branch, and present analyses of ATL letters. Our analyses point to increased Indigenous mobilisation in response to political attacks by the far-right government in power between 2019 and 2022. Indigenous peoples organised in their movements assumed a leading role in social resistance against fascism in Brazil.

Keywords

Brazil, extreme right, indigenous peoples, resistance, Free Land Camp.

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Introduction

The effort to reflect on the resistance of Indigenous peoples in Brazil against political violence by the extreme right between 2019 and 2022 is based on previous research about the meanings of genocide in the context of the coronavirus pandemic (Resende, Martinelli, Martinelli, 2022) and about extremist discourses and practices against Indigenous peoples in Brazil (Martinelli, 2022). By compiling and analysing projects and discourses developed during the 2019-2022 administration, we believe it is possible to apprehend the discourses that guided government policies and the impacts of this line of argument for relevant actors involved in issues related to Indigenous peoples in Brazil today. This mapping can be a foundation for analysing the letters produced during the Free Land Camps (Acampamento Terra Livre – ATL) from 2019 to 2022, manifesting acts of resistance against extremist, violent, and genocidal discourses and practices.

To gather information that supports a consistent analysis of practical-discursive action regarding Indigenous peoples, with special attention to the theme of territory demarcation, we conducted bibliographical research on key concepts from the decoloniality framework. We reflected upon the Indigenous issue from a perspective of practical-discursive resistance. We started by mapping government policies and discourses the extreme right administration used regarding Indigenous peoples and their territories.

In another study, we used this database, collated with data presented in reports produced by relevant entities on the current situation of Indigenous populations in Brazil, in a qualitative discursive analysis aided by software (Martinelli, 2022). By choosing to resume the discursive analysis of the speeches of the then-chief executive in Brazil as a backdrop, we seek to establish a link between present-day Brazil and the nation-state constituted by European colonial invasion and exploitation through a violent process marked by widespread genocide, inequality and injustice anchored in racialisation. The imposition of this social organisation model took place at the expense of degrading and destroying, both epistemologically and materially, other ways of being and knowing the world. Yet Indigenous peoples from the territory now known as Brazil resist and maintain their cultures and traditions – a movement against which the Brazilian state has often presented itself as an enemy.

In this paper, we seek to highlight how the discursive production resulting from the largest Indigenous conference in Brazil – the *Acampamento Terra Livre* (Free Land Camp) (ATL), which has been held annually since 2004 – responded to attacks by the federal executive power, acting on discourses previously mapped in presidential speeches. The article is thus organised into five sections: 1. Theoretical-methodological framework; 2. Presentation of concepts relevant to discuss the decolonial turn; 3. Delineation of contexts of attack and resistance regarding the rights of indigenous peoples during the period in question; 4. Summary of the results from previous analyses of chief executive speeches, and 5. Analyses of ATL letters. Final considerations follow the sections in the paper.

1. The data and the critical discourse approach

For the previous study that serves as a foundation here, bibliographical research was conducted on sovereignty and territory, seen from a critical perspective and focusing on Indigenous issues and the decoloniality framework (Martinelli, 2022). These approaches were based on historical,

discursive, and policy mappings, analyses, and considerations of the compiled data. We mapped the policies implemented between 2019 and 2022 and pronouncements mentioning Indigenous peoples and their territories and conducted a critical discourse analysis of his speeches. We aimed to contribute to the critical reflection of government action toward Indigenous peoples while considering the Brazilian history of Indigenous policies and their constitutional rights to the demarcation of territories, meant to guarantee the protection and perpetuation of traditional native cultures.

The source of the material compiled about the discourse production on Indigenous peoples by the former president was the column “Bolsonário,” published by a Brazilian magazine called *Revista Piauí*. The team hired by the magazine provided the database, including the transcription of official speeches, scattered interviews, and live channels by the former president. To complete this database, we carried out non-exhaustive searches on websites of government institutions (FUNAI, IBGE, SESAI, DOU), news agencies (*Agência Brasil*, *EBC*, *Agência Senado*), and press vehicles (*Folha de São Paulo*, *Portal UOL* and *O Globo*). The aim was to plot an extensive map of the discursive production by the former president in his speeches about Indigenous peoples in the online spaces used for communicating with the population and by news agencies regarding the president.

We also analysed data on land demarcation, invasions of Indigenous territories and violence perpetrated during the Bolsonaro government, chiefly based on the “Reports on Violence against Indigenous Peoples,” published by the Missionary Indigenist Council (*Conselho Indigenista Missionário* - CIMI) in 2021 and 2022, the reports of Human Rights Watch (HRW), the World Resources Institute (WRI) and the Socio-Environmental Institute (*Instituto Socioambiental* - ISA), including its platform *Povos Indígenas do Brasil* (PIB). These data were used in previous studies about presidential speeches on the subject and the anti-indigenous policies implemented in that administration, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, as the reports point out (Martinelli, 2022).

In the present study, a summary of the results of this analytical effort will serve as a backdrop to analyse the responses of Indigenous movements to political violence threatening their rights. The data are composed of documents collected from 2019, 2020, 2021, and 2022 ATL letters. These letters resulting from the ATL meetings obviously cannot communicate all the conflicts, demands and positions of the more than 300 Indigenous peoples in Brazil. They are succinct political documents that aim to summarise public statements and current critical points that are collectively listed. For the 5 days of each annual meeting, discussions are systematised, and the letter is written by a committee that includes leaders of the Indigenous movement.

We analysed presidential speeches and ATL documents using critical discourse studies (CDS) tools. CDS perceives “the linguistic and visual resources of texts as subtle indicators of the hegemonic struggle for the establishment of truth” (Chouliaraki, 2005: 50).

In this sense, CDS focuses on language as social practice and representation of practice. Discourse is thus “not only analysed as an autonomous spoken object but also as a situated interaction, as a social practice or as a type of communication in a social, cultural, historical or political situation” (van Dijk, 2015:12). This is why the methods used in critical discourse studies focus on the relationships between social structure and discourse structure (Fairclough, 2010; Resende, 2017).

The interdiscursive perspective identifies the articulation of many discourses. The analyses regarding lexical choices, recurrency of word patterns, representation strategies, and value assessments in the textual structures (Vieira, Resende, 2016) were useful for plotting discourses about Indigenous peoples and the organised collective response. Thus, both sets of analyses—presidential speeches echoing the reactionary right wing and collective discourses showing resistance of Indigenous peoples—are anchored in discourse as a powerful dimension of social reality.

2. Horizons of meanings in the decolonial perspective: epistemicide, ethnocide and ecocide

The imposition of modern European science on the world brought with it the importation of essentially colonial knowledge forms, marked by dichotomisation – an inherent characteristic of modern science. The epistemic privilege granted to Western science, which fundamentally diminishes the knowledge produced by other bodies of knowledge, has created the dangerous epistemic trap of defining the truth, reality, and what is understood as being best for others.

The construct of dichotomous difference by opposition (Collins, 2016), used to support systems of oppression by categorising people and ideas in terms of their differences, is typical of Westernized science, marked by colonialities and epistemic privileges. In this sense, the binary “reason/emotion, culture/nature, fact/opinion, mind/body, and subject/object, gain meaning only concerning its counterpart,” which is opposite and not complementary (Collins, 2016: 108). The fragility of this dichotomous distinction is resolved and legitimised by the exercise of power and domination.

The massive genocides led by European imperialist undertakings also promoted “epistemicide” – the obliteration of existing knowledge through violence and destruction. Moreover, coloniality is also manifested by the perpetuation of epistemicide (Fricker, 2007), including the context and types of relationships established between Indigenous peoples and nation-states.

Ethnocide and ecocide are concepts often evoked as a legal basis for Indigenous resistance against recurring, institutionalised, and even state-promoted violence in an articulated and integrated effort of the continued genocide led by the European invasion. On this topic, Gersen Baniwa states that

ethnocide is a set of practices that seek, through ‘cultural integration,’ to remove/deny the Indigenous person’s sense of belonging to their language, knowledge, ways of life, and ethnic identity. The goal is that, as soon as they are ‘integrated’ and homogenised, the indigenous people cease to be what they are. It is, therefore, one of the primary forms of extermination and negation of Indigenous lives (Baniwa, 2006, s/p).

The ethnocidal practice has been an integral component of the Brazilian state since its inception – the will to impose widespread nationalist sentiment based on coloniality as a source of unity, with the purpose of unification, is characterised as ethnocide. This violence seeks a generic dissolution by homogenising the different population groups that occupy the Brazilian territory while imposing a supposed unification that complies with the official discourse of national identity (Longhini, 2021).

Ethnocide in the Brazilian State was institutionalised until the Constitutional Framework of

1988 (Brazil, 1988). The indigenist policy before the Constitution, called ‘integralist,’ held as its primary objective the integration and gradual ‘insertion’ of indigenous peoples into capitalist and westernised society until there would no longer be distinct nations and their different ways of being and thinking about the world. For the state, ‘Indigenous’ meant a transitory social category until the assimilated Indigenous person became part of the other non-indigenous racial categories in an official and institutionalised form. Geni Longhini (2021) highlights the central role of compulsory Christianization in this process, which played and still plays a violent role in designating a stamp of ‘unbelonging’ to the original life forms in this land.

Ethnocide is anchored in the essentialist perspective that the Indigenous inhabits the past. This outlook reinforces the colonial understanding of the linearity of ‘development’ that culminates in the urban-normative white man. For Tupinambá (2019), it constitutes “the denial of our existence by stating that, to be considered Indian or *Quilombola*, a person needs to live as their ancestors did in the 16th Century”, a perception from which stems the discourse that indigenous populations cause a delay in the country’s development. It is also anchored in a homogenising ideal, which bunches hundreds of Brazilian ethnic groups as one people while ignoring the cultural, linguistic, religious, and phenotypic diversity of each Indigenous nation. Non-recognition of this existent plurality is essential for implementing the integrationist invisibility project forged by the state (Longhini, 2021).

Ecocide defines environmental devastation as a crime that impacts nature and its natural cycles, causes damage to life forms (whether human or non-human), is committed by act or omission, and can also be committed by states or businesses in strict liability (Ecocid Act, 2012). It implies extensive, severe, and systematic destruction or loss of an ecosystem in a territory (Gordilho, Ravazzano, 2017). The meaning of territoriality and ecosystem preservation for indigenous peoples and traditional communities is often delegitimised, underestimated (da Cunha et al., 2021), or understood from a limiting Westernized perspective. From a modern scientific standpoint, the possibilities for environmental management tend to ignore the relationship often established by Indigenous peoples to their territory, one of profound integration and belonging, which represents a complex network of interrelationships between living and non-living beings, human and non-human agents (Ingold, 2011; Krenak, 2020).

For many Indigenous peoples and traditional communities, continuing to exist and perpetuating non-Western cultures is a challenge that the state often poses as the enemy. Indeed, the expropriation of indigenous lands began at the time of the intrusion, and this violence continues to be routinely exercised. Indigenous authors such as Edson Kaiapó question the official narrative about what has been called the ‘discovery’ of Brazil, a story of invasion, exploitation, genocide, and erasure. The discourse associated with the Brazilian territory, depicted as previously a ‘land without an owner,’ has legitimised the expropriation and the discourses and practices of land ownership (Kayapó, Brito, 2015).

Since then, structural racism has been based on the colonialities inherited from the European invasion and on the “belief in the existence of naturally hierarchical races due to the intrinsic relationship between the physical and moral, physical and intellectual, physical and cultural” (Munanga, 2013: 8). In this perspective, racialised peoples distance themselves from the entire position of humanity, reinforcing the colonising linearity. “The perception of the westernised white person as a universal representative of the human race leads to the consideration of the premise: “whoever is not white is not that human” (Faustino, 2017: 128).

3. Anti-indigenous policies and resistance in Brazil under the far-right

During the 2018 presidential campaign in Brazil, the far-right candidate said that “not a single centimetre more” of Indigenous lands would be further demarcated in his 2019-2022 administration. In January 2019, already elected, he commanded an administrative restructuring that transferred the task of delimiting Indigenous Territories to the Ministry of Agriculture, an attempt barred by the Federal Supreme Court (STF). In August 2019, he reasserted that, as president, he would not demarcate any more Indigenous territories and that no government act would be established in favour of Indigenous issues. Faced with this anti-indigenous policy, some actions by social groups sought to assure that the rights already conquered by Indigenous peoples would be respected:

- In 2019, the Human Rights Lawyers Collective and the Arns Commission presented a report to the International Criminal Court accusing the president of “crimes against humanity” and “incitement to genocide and widespread, systematic attacks against Indigenous Peoples”, in addition to reducing inspection and displaying omission in the prevention of environmental crimes in the Amazon (ISA, 2020);
- at the 19th Session of the United Nations Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues, held in April 2019, the Association of Indigenous Peoples of Brazil (APIB) issued complaints against the federal administration, highlighting the president’s hate speech;
- in 2020, the non-compliance with a fundamental precept (ADPF n. 709) presented by the Association at the Federal Supreme Court pointed to irresponsibility regarding public health and institutional racism against Indigenous peoples as the causes of the “ongoing genocide” (APIB, 2020);
- At the 20th session of the United Nations Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues in April 2021, leaders of several Brazilian Indigenous peoples accused the president of genocide, highlighting the suspension of Indigenous land demarcation, intensification of territorial conflicts, invasions of Indigenous territories, government inaction during the COVID-19 pandemic healthcare crisis, and the upsurge of violence through invasions of Indigenous lands.

Social organisations also produced several reports during this period. For example, in 2020, the Federal University of Minas Gerais and the Socio-Environmental Institute released a report pointing to a “risk of genocide with the complicity of the Brazilian State” for the Yanomami people (ISA, 2020). In 2022, a Human Rights Watch report denounced how the administration weakened government agencies responsible for protecting Indigenous rights, issued regulations harmful to people, and withdrew budgets from federal environmental protection agencies. These actions left territories even more vulnerable to invasions, land grabbing, and violence (HRW, 2022).

The federal administration in Brazil, led by the extreme right, has paralysed demarcation procedures for protected areas, including Indigenous lands. The Ministry of Justice withdrew a series of ordinances by the National Foundation for the Indigenous Peoples (FUNAI) that were ready to be published; other declaratory ordinances were annulled; processes that were already in progress administratively receded; and ordinances interdicting and restricting use for monitoring and protecting isolated peoples expired.

The management of the pandemic by the government about the original peoples was also criticised. The lack of guarantee of basic healthcare related to COVID-19 only started to be reversed with the mandatory emergency actions imposed by the Federal Supreme Court (CIMI,

2022). Mining permissions increased significantly, mainly in the Amazon region. In the Yanomami Indigenous Land alone, there were more than 500 overlapping applications for exploitation, adding up to more than 3 million hectares. CIMI recorded, in 2021, 305 cases of land invasions, illegal exploitation of natural resources, and various damages to property, which affected at least 226 Indigenous lands across the country. Reports of abuse of power in the territories more than doubled, pointing to the invasion of villages by armed men, brutal searches, and threats to open fire against Indigenous (CIMI, 2022).

In 2021, 19 death threats were recorded, encompassing two communities in Mato Grosso and Maranhão. In the 2022 CIMI report, the country’s disrespectful administration and the presidential discourse are identified as drivers for acts of violence and discrimination. For example, criminal groups enticed children and teenagers into human trafficking, and Indigenous adults and children were co-opted for slave-like conditions of labour.

FUNAI, the agency assigned to protect indigenous rights, underwent a series of transformations during the Bolsonaro administration. In 2018, before the presidential inauguration, the then-candidate criticised the foundation for protecting Indigenous rights and promised his electorate he would endorse budget cuts. Marcelo Xavier, appointed in 2019 by the president of the country to preside over the Foundation, discharged tenured civil in leadership positions, filed persecutory investigations against FUNAI employees, Indigenous leaders, and prosecutors in defence of Indigenous rights; invoked red tape to delay or bar initiatives to protect Indigenous territories; and adopted policies that boosted invasion and violence (HRW, 2022). Persecution at the institution was recorded in announcements of unjustified dismissals, removals, and relocations carried out without prior notice or formal explanation. The report “Anti-Indigenous Foundation: The Portrayal of Funai under the Bolsonaro Government” was published by the Institute of Socioeconomic Studies and Associated Indigenists (INESC, INA, 2022).

Actively anti-indigenous policies led civil society to act urgently against the lack of resources and institutional/governmental support. Some examples stand out throughout the administration, such as the case of the Indigenous Association of Vale do Javari (UNIVAJA), which was forced to promote patrols in the forest to protect against territorial invasions in their territories since they suffered from the complete absence of state protection (HRW, 2022). Attacks against the Munduruku Wakoborũn Women’s Association in March 2021 by miners were recorded in videos released by the community. The more potent case is the emblematic escalation of violence against the Yanomami and Ye’kwana peoples, with attacks perpetrated by thousands of illegal miners against Indigenous people also recorded (CIMI, 2022), and the routine practice of sexual violence in Yanomami territory by prospectors invading the territory. The repression and murder of defenders of Indigenous peoples also marked the administration. In 2019, Funai agent Maxciel Pereira dos Santos was executed in Tabatinga, in the state of Amazonas. An emblematic case of violence against indigenists occurred in 2019 when FUNAI agent Bruno Pereira organised a significant operation to inspect and expel illegal mining in the Javari Valley. His investigative mission culminated in a major police action that destroyed 60 criminally operating rafts. A few days later, the agent was removed from the coordinator position of the Foundation’s Isolated Indigenous Peoples Division and transferred to another branch without a leadership position (HRW, 2022). About two years later, in 2022, Bruno Pereira and journalist Dom Phillip were murdered in Vale do Javari.

From 2019 to 2022, the anti-indigenous agendas and discourses materialised through different practices, such as the increase in Amazon deforestation (HRW, 2022), the weakening of

environmental inspection agencies and mechanisms, expense cuts for these areas, institutional persecution, encouragement of invasions, cases of violence and murder, increase in mining permissions and the number of illegal prospectors working in Indigenous territories. The stoppage of demarcations and the encouragement of prospecting, logging, and farming activities have created an undeniably unsafe environment for Indigenous peoples in Brazil.

4. Live broadcasts, interviews, and the press: summary of extremist representation of Indigenous peoples

The column “Bolsonário,” published by the Brazilian magazine *Revista Piauí*, exposed the former president’s preference for giving speeches on his own (in live broadcasts produced by his team) rather than speaking in press conferences. In lives streamed on social media in 2019, for example, the president used more than 131,000 words, more than double the number used in interviews given to the press during the same period (Almeida, Rossi, Buono, 2019).

The words “Indigenous” and “Indian” were mentioned 61 times, and all mentions of traditional peoples carried a negative connotation, usually depicted in accusations of a “demarcation fever” of reservations that would supposedly divide the people and render the agribusiness project unfeasible. In the interview transcripts, the representative mentioned Indigenous peoples on 10 occasions identified by the search terms “demarcation,” “Indigenous,” and “Indian” (the keywords “peoples” and “original/native” did not lead to any related theme, which is a significant absence). In the transcripts of live broadcasts, mentions of Indigenous peoples, found by the same search keys, were identified on 13 occasions (the keys “peoples” and “original/native” did not lead to any related theme either). To the data provided by *Revista Piauí* in its survey, we added data collected from government portals, news agencies, and press vehicles chosen for their relevance in terms of reach.

The speeches made by Bolsonaro to address issues related to Indigenous peoples, articulated with the policies and projects proposed and implemented in his administration or associated with the demarcation of Indigenous Lands, the National Indian Foundation, the protection of the environment and protected territories in Brazil, had disastrous consequences and represented a step backwards. This milestone has, from now on, irreparable consequences – lives were lost, including those of elders who retained traditional knowledge, represented native cultures, and symbolised important roles; hectares of native forests were devastated; Indigenous territories were invaded and exploited; human rights were violated; plus, all the institutional, cultural, social and environmental consequences already mentioned.

Recurrent discourses present in the speeches of the then-president associate Indigenous peoples with a sense of animalisation and evolutionism. The former president repeatedly inferred that Indigenous peoples were not whole human beings and, not being considered fully human, a state of transition is assumed in which they would evolve towards being “increasingly human like us” (his words). This presupposes an evolutionary reference that would culminate in the “us” pole, evoked by the white-man-urban-capitalist speaker, as if there were a linear evolution of the species, with the Indigenous placed in the transitory between the animal and the “evolved human being” (his words again). Ethnocide is then assumed as a solution for the “humanisation” of Indigenous peoples, acquired through “integration into society” and assimilation to the “us” group based on the reference to urban whiteness. It directly evades the pre-constitutional integrationist argument, understanding ethnocide as an evolutionary path.

The co-text patterns most frequently activated manifest repetition about Indigenous peoples belonging to a time in the past and their supposed wish to integrate or achieve “modernisation” towards the white and European development model. This assumption creates a justification for the violent acts perpetrated by the government. The repetition of sentences structured as “now the Indian will be able to use the land like the farmer does” reveals an association between Indigenous peoples and human beings from the past (even ‘prehistoric,’ in the words of the representative) or non-human (when he compares indigenous lands to zoos).

For example, at an event held in Rio de Janeiro, when he was debating environmental issues and plans for the region of Angra dos Reis (an area that includes an ecological station and a Guarani Indigenous territory) in July 2019, Bolsonaro stated:

I've been talking to Indians; they don't want to live like prehistoric people on their lands; they want electricity first. I was now in the Amazon and spoke to a small group of Indians. That was the conversation. The Indian is a human being like us; it is not to be isolated in a reserve as if it were a zoo.

Justification is created for the ethnocidal policy – seen as an alternative to humanise, to bring to the present, to ‘advance’ in the racist linear perspective of development. These discourses are anchored in the integrationist perception of the indigenist policy applied during the dictatorship before the landmark of the 1988 Federal Constitution. By its ethnocidal nature, the integrationist discourse propagates that there are no social organisations and ways of being in the world other than those imposed by the white-Western-capitalist model.

On the other hand, the then-president suggested that he was doing the Indigenous peoples a favour, arguing that allowing third parties to exploit Indigenous lands for agriculture, livestock, mining, and logging would be in the interest of the native peoples themselves. He also suggests that Indigenous cultures and traditional ways of life represent in themselves a setback from which Indigenous peoples would like to leave to evolve. These topics, which are conflicting agendas in discourse and practice, are not adhered to by Indigenous movements. On the contrary, the prevalent discourse is contrary to any land leasing, including the position of *Articulação dos Povos Indígenas do Brasil - APIB* (Articulation of Indigenous Peoples in Brazil). Furthermore, such permission would be unconstitutional.

When discussing Indigenous lands and the environment, he refers to these territories and the Amazon as mining hotspots, frequently highlighting the extraction of niobium and graphite as opportunities and potential spaces for agribusiness. This view corroborates the colonial dichotomisation, which perceives the environment solely as a source for extracting natural resources and generating economic profit, which is opposed to Indigenous peoples’ perceptions of belonging to the territory (Krenak, 2020).

In the transcripts of speeches and interviews, as well as in the texts published by news agencies and portals reporting on presidential speeches, the ‘demarcation’ of Indigenous lands is represented by the president as an ‘industry,’ as something done on a large scale and evoking a negative meaning. He questions the financial cost of demarcations, which induces a purely economic understanding of the land and issues his objections against the amount of demarcated land and the possibility of future homologations of territories. His use of the terms ‘Indigenous’ and ‘land’ appears in collocations that activate the metaphors of the “demarcation industry,”

of a “demarcation fever,” or of states “taken by demarcation.” When “Indigenous” appears combined with “reservations,” it represents the territory as unfeasible, unproductive land, obstructing agribusiness and economic exploitation. Indigenous land is referred to as “the most expensive piece of land in the world,” especially in contexts that activate economic meanings (with lexical choices like “lease,” “farm,” “business,” and “owner”).

The articulated analysis between (i) the projects and policies proposed for Indigenous peoples throughout the former presidential administration, (ii) the speeches of the former president, and (iii) the data presented in the reports on violence against Indigenous peoples in Brazil during the period point to an ethnic-ecocidal policy anchored in the regression to integrationist indigenist ideals. This backward step disrespects the constitutional and international rights guaranteed to native peoples.

In the next section, we will discuss the resistance movements Indigenous peoples built to face a violent State. We will analyse four documents produced in the contexts of ATL in 2019, 2020, 2021, and 2022, coinciding with the period of the presidential statements we discussed here. To analyse the ATL documents, we will search for the Indigenous organisations' responses to Bolsonaro's speeches. We will ask ourselves how they deconstruct the meanings present in the presidential speeches.

5. Focus on the resistance: ATL documents from 2019-2022

The emergence of digital platforms has significantly transformed Indigenous activism, providing new spaces for resistance advocacy, amplifying claims and proposals, challenging dominant state narratives, mobilising collective action, and engaging in international advocacy efforts (Duarte, 2017). Social media enables the practice of visibility politics, enforcing treaty responsibilities, and shedding light on violence and inequity. Digital engagement allows Indigenous peoples to challenge the historical erasure perpetuated by mainstream media and state institutions, being instrumental in documenting state violence, organising protests, and fostering political and social engagement.

Indigenous digital activism fosters transnational solidarity, connecting struggles across regions and movements. The experiences of movements such as the Zapatistas in Mexico, Idle No More in Canada, and Brazilian Indigenous movements highlight how social media, in this case, facilitates coalition-building and the exchange of resistance strategies (Lupien, 2020; Duarte, 2017). These digital connections contribute to a global Indigenous movement, where shared experiences of colonialism, environmental degradation, and state violence are articulated collectively. Transnational networks enhance domestic and international political leverage, challenging state-imposed narratives of isolation and marginalisation and positioning global movements for justice and decolonisation.

Acampamento Terra Livre—ATL (Free Land Camp) is the largest mobilisation assembly of Indigenous peoples in Brazil and probably worldwide. It exemplifies how Indigenous movements use digital tools to amplify their struggles. The ATL's strategic use of digital media demonstrates how Indigenous activism transcends physical borders, fostering transnational alliances. However, as the annual ATL meeting shows, the physical presence remains central to this assembly. ATL has been held annually since 2004, as a rule, in Brasilia (with exceptions in 2010 and 2012, when the meeting took place in other Brazilian cities, and online in 2020 due to the pandemic). Its past 18 editions have brought together several peoples to discuss violations

of rights, claim compliance with laws, and propose resistance actions, such as the very creation of the *Articulação dos Povos Indígenas do Brasil* - APIB (Articulation of Indigenous Peoples in Brazil), a result of the first edition of ATL. The 2022 edition brought together more than 200 different peoples, according to APIB.

The public letters from each ATL meeting present “the movement’s political reading of governments”. They explicitly position Indigenous policies and structures and record their historical demands and claims. The main agenda of the ATL has been the issue of territory – defending demarcation rights and seeking respect to already demarcated territories, the right to difference, self-determination, and autonomy, alongside issues of access to health and education, complaints of recurrent violence and, more recently, intersectional issues such as the rights of Indigenous women, the Indigenous LGBT population, Indigenous youth, Indigenous in the prison system.

During the period we are focusing on, from 2019 to 2022, four ATL assemblies were held, of which two were in-person, one was hybrid, and one was hybrid. In 2020, the pandemic prevented the meeting, so the event took place online, and the 2021 edition was hybrid. The themes of the four editions were as follows: “We have resisted for 519 years and will continue to resist” (2019), “Occupying the networks and demarcating the screens” (2020), “Our fight is still for life, it is not just a virus” (2021) and “Reclaiming Brazil: demarcating territory and politics” (2022).

For this study of discursive disputes, we analyse four documents resulting from each ATL meeting during the established period. Using the NVivo software, we coded the thematic correspondences with the discourses previously raised in the presidential speeches. Therefore, the criteria for selecting and coding themes within the NVivo software were these correspondences with Bolsonaro’s speeches. The coding process in NVivo is manual: inductively from the texts and through careful reading.

The taken-up meanings that we encoded in the software were the following: racism and hate speech; integrationist policy; invasion of Indigenous lands (illegal occupation, mining, and agribusiness); anti-indigenous policies and laws; environmental and climate issues; demarcation of territories. In addition to these themes, other recurrent themes in the ATL documents were inductively mapped: social participation and the indigenous movement, the head of the executive branch, and his government. Other topics also addressed in the ATL documents were health, education, pandemic, well-being, religious imposition, and international treaties.

The most recurrent meanings in the presidential speeches – of animalisation and evolutionism – are not directly resumed in the documents of the Indigenous movement, which, however, trigger the themes of racism, genocide, and ethnocide several times: “We are victims of trespassing, dispossession, destruction, violence, prejudice, discrimination, racism; in short, of ethnocidal and genocidal policies and practices.” Regarding this, the presidential discourse is mentioned to denounce the association of his speeches to the anti-indigenous policy: “Using speeches laden with racism and hate, Bolsonaro encourages violence against our communities and paralyzes the actions of the state that is supposed to promote assistance, protection, and guarantee of rights”.

In 2019, the most common themes were Indigenous peoples' rights, land demarcation, health care, and education (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Mapping of the 20 most recurrent words used at ATL in 2019.

Source: Author's analysis of NVivo.

In 2020, health issues linked to COVID-19 and territory were recurring topics, with direct references to the government, namely the former president and FUNAI (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Mapping of the 20 most recurrent words used at ATL in 2020.

Source: Author's analysis of NVivo.

In 2021, the most recurrent themes were the pandemic, territory, and the Indigenous struggle (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Mapping of the 20 most recurrent words used at ATL in 2021.

Source: Author's analysis of NVivo.

Finally, the 2022 document addresses the Indigenous struggle and the rights to territory (Figure 4).

Figure 4 – Mapping of the 20 most recurrent words used at ATL in 2022.

Source: Author’s analysis of NVivo.

The word clouds generated with the 20 most frequently used words in each document reveal the constant presence of the possessive “*nossos* (ours)”: in 2019, the most recurrent collocation is “*nossos direitos*” (our rights); in 2020, “*nossos indígenas*” (our Indigenous peoples); in 2021, “*nossos povos*” (our peoples), and in 2022, “*nossos territórios*” (our territories).

The recurrent presence of the possessive pronoun suggests the analytical relevance of the oppositions activated in the discourse. In the 2019 document, Indigenous peoples are articulated in opposition to the “growing wave of invasions, land division, deforestation, land leases and violence, illegal and criminal practices that constitute a new phase of the dispossession of our lands, which violate our right of exclusive usufruct”.

This metaphorical “*onda crescente*” (rising wave) and undefined ‘enemy’ give way to more specific polarity expressions. In 2020, directly mentioning the former president, his minister of agriculture, and the rural lobby: “Bolsonaro, as soon as he took office, (...) transferred the part of environmental licensing and demarcation of Indigenous lands to the Ministry of Agriculture, commanded by the rural lobby, the enemy of our peoples, personified in the farmer Minister Teresa Cristina”.

In 2021, the opposition is built, first, against colonial history itself (“the European invasion of our traditional territories”) and its continuity in the present (“the assassins were rewarded with the occupation of our lands and territories”). Afterwards, it takes the form of the current, concrete, and tangible enemy, the former Brazilian government, mentioning the president by name (“With the election of the current president, Jair Bolsonaro, our peoples were once again targeted”) and referring to the conflicts “fed by the government itself to divide, weaken and demobilising our peoples” and the “negligence and disregard of this hateful and racist policy”. In 2022, opposition to the federal government remains central in the ATL letter: “Bolsonaro encouraged invasions of our territories and violence against our relatives”, and then unfolds into various enemies, assimilated as “devastating undertakings” and linked to the then chief executive: “The current president is still working to legalise the activities of criminal organisations that operate in the territories: miners, loggers, cattle ranchers, militiamen, and land grabbers”.

The 2022 document ends provocatively and articulates a collective and necessary struggle using the possessive pronouns mentioned previously. The culminating message depicted by the Indigenous struggle is relevant beyond the issue strictly regarding native peoples, as it is also a

social, political, and environmental struggle: “Our struggle is for our peoples, yes, but also for the future of all Brazilian and all of humanity! We fight for a civilising project for the country and the world”. In this articulation of the Indigenous struggle as a “future” and a “civilising project”, the document counter-strikes (Bispo dos Santos, 2015) recurring evolutionist discourses embedded in the presidential speeches. The same deconstruction movement in the discursive dispute is observed when the ATL rejects the perspective of anachronistic isolation, placing itself as a relevant collective actor and articulating with other movements, including in the digital space:

Thus, combined with the struggles in our territories, the permanent mobilisations, along with national and international society, and the occupation of virtual territories, hand in hand with movements and allied sectors of society, we will remove with time and collective action the current scenario of capitalist barbarism, fascist hatred and structural racism inherent to this system. (ATL, 2022, without page number)

In the context of the fierce presidential race that year, the 2022 document expands the meanings already present in previous documents to invest not only in the previously given oppositions but also in partnerships and coalitions. In the 2019 document, the predominant tone is demanding; in 2020 and 2021, condemnation (Figure 5); in 2022, provoking (Figure 6). Considering the four documents and crossing the tone mapping with the themes taken up from the previously analysed presidential speech, the tone of condemnation is the most recurrent response to dealing with hate speech, anti-indigenous projects, and invasions of territories.

Figure 5 – Mapping of the 50 most recurrent words in the condemning tone.

Source: Author’s analysis of NVivo.

The provocative tone is more commonly used when thematising Indigenous movements' social participation in association with other social movements, especially in 2022.

The dire consequences manifested in the humanitarian crisis had been previously alerted, strengthening the allegations of genocide against the extreme right-wing government in Brazil. May an attentive look at this recent past and its connections with our terrible past allow us to build another future.

Conclusion

The discourses that the former president aligned with promoted an ethno-ecocidal policy that boosted physical, patrimonial, and psychological violence against native peoples, the violation of Indigenous lands, and environmental degradation. The violation of the rights guaranteed to indigenous peoples by the federal constitution and by international agreements of which Brazil is a signatory represented an obstacle to the perpetuation of traditional cultures and the guarantee of safety and dignity of the native peoples of Brazil.

However, organised in social movements, assuming several discursive spaces, including online spaces, and disputing political power, Brazilian Indigenous peoples have represented a decisive action against the extreme right. In addition to the ATL documents, which are the focus of this article, Brazilian Indigenous leaders have stood out in legal, political, and academic environments in fighting against fascism on a national and international scale.

The efforts of Indigenous movements against genocide have gained international prominence in recent years. In 2019, the claim of non-compliance with a fundamental precept, presented by APIB and registered in the Federal Supreme Court, pointed to healthcare irresponsibility and institutional racism against Indigenous peoples as the causes of the “ongoing genocide.” Even before the allegations of genocide against the former president became a political agenda, Indigenous peoples, with internationally recognised reasons, were already pointing out the crimes committed. In 2021, more than 160,000 people signed an Open Letter to the Federal Supreme Court for demarcating Indigenous lands. APIB published the International Dossier on Brazilian Indigenous Peoples' claims the same year.

Digital activism represents a transformative tool for Indigenous movements to amplify struggles, document systemic violence, and mobilise transnational networks and support. This activism fosters and strengthens political advocacy and Indigenous participation in domestic and international agendas, besides influencing public opinion and policy decisions. The strategic dissemination of information through digital platforms not only raises awareness of Indigenous struggles but also applies pressure on political institutions to address issues such as land demarcation, environmental degradation, and systemic violence against Indigenous communities. Indigenous participation in political decisions is crucial to inclusive and sustainable governance models that reflect the diverse realities of Indigenous communities.

Digital activism interacts with offline mobilisation strategies, particularly in contexts of structural violence, overlapping vulnerabilities, state repression and risks to Indigenous peoples and activists (Lupien, 2020). Indigenous transnational resistance movements influence global policy frameworks, especially regarding Indigenous rights and socioenvironmental protection, strengthening local and global networks. Examining these transnational connections in future research can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of Indigenous resistance as a critical force in shaping national and international policy agendas.

Four years of the far right administration in Brazil have left a desolate legacy: preventable deaths, in addition to deaths that cannot be estimated (including institutional neglect with the production of data about and for Indigenous peoples); native knowledge of the land threatened and lost; entire populations living in hunger, poverty, and various social vulnerabilities; invaded, violated and occupied Indigenous territories; burned and degraded native forests; mercury-contaminated rivers; losses in biodiversity and incalculable impacts on ecosystems. These effects have their most visible manifestation in the humanitarian crisis experienced by the Yanomami People. Gradually, the (in)action of the Brazilian state during that administration became public as growing evidence revealed the anti-indigenous action observed in hindering territory demarcations, drastically reducing state protection forces in the territories, scrapping the state apparatus responsible for Indigenous issues in the absence or lack of basic medical and health care for Indigenous and traditional peoples, including in the context of the pandemic; in the attempts to pass permissive laws and regulations that benefitted invasions of indigenous lands and in the actively pro-mining discourse marked by prejudice against the indigenous peoples of Brazil.

Little by little, the responsibility for such actions and their sad, incalculable, and irrecoverable consequences will be judged in national and international legal frameworks. Justice will be served. The future can only be ancestral.

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